

What does the pandemic teach us on complex systems?

Complexity created the pandemic and amplified some of its impacts

Relatively small disease outbreak in a wildlife market in China very quickly escalated across the globe – only four months ago. Why did the outbreak start in the first place? Increased interactions between humans and wildlife, humans invading their habitats and coming in closer contact than safely advisable. Animals are a major source of viruses for humans.

This is an extreme example of non-linear interactions, which have been either amplified or dampened on their way across countries. The baffling **speed** of the propagation reflects 21st century complexity: large-scale international travel and tightly-coupled economies. This is a downside of a large number of dynamic Interactions.

How does this speed compare to the Spanish flu pandemic (1918), which also spread quickly due to the movement of soldiers during WWI? What about earlier pandemics?

Complexity has also amplified the impacts of the pandemic – e.g. healthcare supply chains designed to work just-in-time (i.e. low inventories, tightly-coupled supply chains) have not been able to cope with the surge in demand for cheap supplies, such as face masks. Overreliance on cheap foreign suppliers of critical healthcare supplies creates additional complexity (i.e. interactions) and scarcity of resources – all countries competing for the same limited supplies. Is capitalism consuming our resilience?

The pandemic has also made it clear that not all elements are equal in complex systems: diversity of power and income (between countries and individuals) might either amplify or dampen the impacts of the pandemic. E.g. rich going to their second homes in the countryside, developing nations not able to buy necessary supplies. In countries like Brazil, the epidemic started at the middle class with people who were abroad on holidays. At the end, the poorer are likely to be hit hardest. Preliminary evidence from the U.S. suggests this is already happening there – poor people have been disproportionately affected in several regions. Hope: the virus arrived later in developing countries and lockdowns have been in place since earlier stages of the outbreak. Positive signs that this has paid back in some South American countries, like Argentina and Paraguay.

Complex responses to cope with the pandemic

Lockdowns, quarantines, social distancing, and closing of borders aim at lowering complexity for a short period (first response was to fight complexity by destroying it - i.e. breaking down the chain of interactions - the same measure that has been adopted for centuries in previous pandemics). This has bought some slack to develop sustainable resilience and complex responses.

Complexity has played a role in many ways to cope with this crisis – most measures can be best framed as informed judgments with no certainties, instead of unambiguous solutions.

Some of the coping approaches are presented below, considering their links with a set of guidelines for coping with complexity (Bueno et al., 2019¹).

Taking advantage of diverse perspectives

- Sharing of information among healthcare professionals. Knowledge on the virus has evolved at an unprecedented speed partly due to collaborative efforts worldwide. Good example of working across boundaries;
- Large international clinical trials led by WHO and other organisations (e.g. discovery trial, solidarity trial);
- Diversity of perspectives for coping with the wider societal effects (economic, psychological/mental health, political, education, etc.);
- Innovative technological and organizational solutions: crisis as a catalyzer for innovation. E.g. re-interpreting existing technologies from another perspective, e.g. diving masks in Italian hospitals, re-interpreting existing drugs for treating covid-19. At our teaching hospital in Brazil, N95 and Pff2 masks have been reused after sterilization – a new protocol has been developed for that purpose;
- Role played by State governors and mayors, in countries like Brazil, Germany, and the U.S. Decentralized decision-making has been helpful for agility and accounting for local context;
- Are all perspectives worth listening? Some discussions, which are mostly technical, have been highly politicized – e.g. use of cloroquine and need for quarantines. Some national leaders (e.g. in Brazil) are seeking political gains and sowing confusion among the population.

Providing slack

- Lots of sources of opportunistic slack have emerged (e.g. volunteers – e.g. students producing face masks at universities, factories changing their production lines, homemade face masks, hotel rooms being used for quarantines, car factories repairing and producing respiratory ventilators);
- Example from Finland: stocks of medical equipment and food developed over decades have been used now. Original intention was to protect the country during the cold war period and possible conflicts with Russia;
- Probably one of the main lessons of this crisis will relate to the need for more (and readily deployable) slack resources in the healthcare system.

Giving visibility to processes and outcomes

- Giving visibility to what is going on is a key (the threat is invisible, including asymptomatic people): need for transparent data on how the outbreak is evolving at local, national, and international levels – e.g. which neighbourhoods are hotspots?

¹ Bueno, W. P., Saurin, T. A., Wachs, P., Kuchenbecker, R., & Braithwaite, J. (2019). Coping with complexity in intensive care units: A systematic literature review of improvement interventions. *Safety Science*, 118, 814-825.

- Some examples of good practices related to this guideline: contact tracing and apps for tracking hotspots in real-time (South Korea), monitoring of compliance with quarantines based on GPS data from mobile phones;
- Immunization certificates will be a key for visibility; it depends on effective antibody tests;
- Visibility can empower people to better protect themselves, supporting resilience at the individual level;
- In many countries visibility has been hindered by vast underreporting of sick people due to the lack of testing.

Understanding work-as-done

- What about work-as-imagined (WAI) on these days at the front-line? Gap between WAI and work-as-done (WAD) has probably been wider than ever. Several otherwise routine activities have changed overnight. It is hard to leave behind the old way of working, which may increase the likelihood of errors. Changes have demanded intensive training and simulation of the new work practices – e.g. new protocols for wearing PPE; there are reports that caregivers have spent more than 1 hour a day wearing protective gear. Add to this the time spent washing hands;
- Need to understand and support WAD on these days; suffering and panic of healthcare professionals - e.g. in our teaching hospital, there are reports that some doctors are going up 13 floors through the stairs instead of using the elevator, caregivers do not hug their children at home.
- There have been adaptations across all levels of healthcare systems, from primary care to ICU.
- Possible opportunity for applying this guideline: to identify high-risk care activities that expose caregivers to the risk of contamination. E.g. wearing protective gear, prone positioning.
- This crisis has shown the huge disconnect between the sharp end/healthcare professionals (WAD) and government officials (WAI), especially in some countries where governments have been in denial and slow in providing a response.

Monitoring unintended consequences

- Many of the adopted coping measures have relevant and obvious unintended consequences (e.g. surveillance, mental health issues, unemployment);
- Implications of higher workload at ICUs on other hospital units. E.g. how medical emergency teams (MET) / rapid response teams, which are based in ICUs and composed by ICU staff, are coping with demand in other hospital units? At our teaching hospital, two separate METs have been created: one for covid-19 patients and another for patients in general. In fact, a general approach has been to develop dedicated patient flows and resources for covid-19;
- What about positive unintended consequences? More solidarity, innovation, less pollution, less work and traffic accidents, rethinking of personal and societal values. How lasting will be those impacts? Which will be the legacy from this? Will we forget and return to business as usual? Experience from past pandemics suggest suggests no reason for much optimism.

Fractal resilient responses to the crisis: aforementioned guidelines apply across micro, meso, and macro levels

Micro: us, our daily behaviour

Meso: healthcare workers/hospitals (micro and macro should be supporting this level – front-line is here)

Macro: government, supply chains, research institutions

What about Safety-I and Safety-II in the pandemic?

News as well as the most visible government responses have been mostly Safety-I oriented – i.e. largely reactive and focused on reducing what goes wrong. For example, the main indicator available to the wider public has been the number of daily deaths.

What a safety-II approach could look like in this pandemic? Tentative examples:

- Micro-level: investigate why most people get infected but do not develop the disease, being asymptomatic.
- Meso level: support resilient performance of caregivers – e.g. provide necessary human and material resources, resting time.
- Macro-level: understand and adapt the approach adopted by countries that have coped most successfully so far (e.g. South Korea, Singapore, Taiwan).

Among the several other indicators that have been made available (number of ICU beds occupied, number of new infections, number of recovered patients, compliance with quarantines, etc.), which have the best predictive power? Possible key indicator, but hard to obtain reliable data: how many people, on average, have been infected by those already infected. There are reports of transmission rates around 2 or 3 (i.e. each infected person transmits the virus to 2 or 3 others). Target is to achieve a rate below 1.0.